

IMPLEMENTATION OF A SYSTEM OF COMFORTABLE DIALOGUE BETWEEN THE INSPECTOR OF PREVENTION, REPRESENTATIVES OF THE MAHALLA AND THE POPULATION ON THE BASIS OF THE "SMART MAHALLA" PROGRAM IN THE TERRITORY OF THE COMMUNITY

Komilov Mirkomil Muhtorovich

Responsible staff member of the Institute for Advanced Training of the
Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan

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Annotation. This article describes the development of the "Smart Mahalla" program, its legal foundations, programmatic content, and its role in the activities of prevention inspectors of the Internal Affairs Department.

keywords: Smart neighborhood, prevention inspector, application, complaint.

Today, maintaining public order and ensuring security, as well as human rights and freedoms, protecting the legitimate interests of society, the state, and the individual from threats of any kind is one of the main factors in ensuring peace and tranquility, interethnic harmony, and sustainable development in the country.

Maintaining and strengthening peace, tranquility and security, civil and interethnic harmony and solidarity in Uzbekistan should remain our most important and decisive task. The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UP-5005 of April 10, 2017, "On Measures to Fundamentally Enhance the Effectiveness of the Activities of Internal Affairs Bodies, Strengthen Their Responsibility for Ensuring Public Order, Reliable Protection of the Rights, Freedoms, and Legitimate Interests of Citizens," identifies instances of negligence and negligence in the reception of representatives of individuals and legal entities by law enforcement officers and the consideration of their appeals, as well as cases of.

In order to ensure the proximity of internal affairs bodies to the population and create convenience for citizens in settlements located far from internal affairs departments (departments), on April 26, 2021, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev signed Decree No. 6196 "On measures to raise the activities of internal affairs bodies to a qualitatively new level in the field of ensuring public safety and combating crime." According to the decree, problems related to the prevention of offenses and the fight against crime in the context of each mahalla, family and individual will be solved directly on the spot.

Mahalla law enforcement centers will be established on the basis of support points of the internal affairs bodies. In 2021, the "Smart Mahalla" information program was launched in Tashkent and Samarkand regions, which allows you to remotely send an appeal to the prevention inspector and monitor the process of its consideration.

The purpose of this project is to prevent crimes and offenses in the region and take timely measures against crimes and offenses, eliminate obstacles between the citizen and the mahalla prevention inspector, and create an opportunity for citizens to directly appeal to the prevention inspector and the mahalla. In addition, it provides for informing the population about the news in the mahalla, legislative and other news, evaluating the work of the prevention inspector and mahalla chairmen by the population. The project also provides for the study and analysis of public opinion on crimes and offenses committed in the region.

To use this application, the citizen downloads the program to his phone using the Internet through the "Play market" or "App store" applications, and registers with a phone number to access the system.

When guests or tourists visit the region, they are given an explanation about the mobile application at the airport, train station, and hotel, and are invited to download this program. After successfully signing up for the program, several opportunities will appear on the home page. One of the main tasks of the preventive inspector is the consideration of appeals from individuals and legal entities.

The daily work of the prevention inspector consists of tasks related to the reception of individuals and legal entities and the consideration of their appeals. Prevention inspectors organize the reception of individuals and legal entities and their representatives in their offices, that is, at the base points of the Internal Affairs Department (TP of the Internal Affairs Department), and the consideration of appeals sent by them remotely. Admission of individuals and legal entities and their representatives is carried out by the head of the state body or other authorized person.

For this purpose, special structural units may be created in state bodies, and officials responsible for admission will be appointed.

Also, the reception of physical and legal persons and their representatives by prevention inspectors and the consideration of appeals sent by them remotely will be held on the specified days and hours in accordance with the reception schedules.

Information on the schedule of admission of preventive inspectors and the time, place of its holding and advance registration for admission, as well as the procedure for admission, shall be brought to the attention of interested parties by posting them on the official websites of state bodies, as well as placing them on public stands or other technical means in their administrative premises.

When an individual applies verbally to preventive inspectors, they must present a document confirming their identity, and a representative of a legal entity - a document confirming their authority, as well as a document confirming their identity.

If the resolution of the issues stated during the personal reception is not within the competence of the prevention inspectors, the applicant is explained to which body or organization it is necessary to apply to resolve the issues stated in the appeal. During the personal reception of preventive inspectors, special technical means (audio and video recording, as well as photography) may be used by decision of the head of the state body and with the written consent of the applicant. When exercising the right to appeal, discrimination based on the gender, race, nationality, language, religion, social origin, beliefs, personal and social status of an individual, as well as the form of ownership, location (postal address), organizational and legal forms and other circumstances of legal entities shall not be allowed.

At this point, it is worth noting the right to appeal. Because the appeals of citizens who come to the reception are one of their inalienable and fundamental rights, a person has the right to appeal in any case. An appeal is an appeal of a person to make recommendations for the exercise of their rights, freedoms and legitimate interests, improvement of the activities of the state and society, as well as restoration of violated rights, freedoms and protection of their legitimate interests. According to the law, every person has the right to directly, together with himself and others, to appeal to competent state bodies, institutions or representatives of the people with applications, proposals and complaints. It is prohibited to unreasonably transfer

to other state bodies for consideration of appeals of persons who have sent remote appeals of preventive inspectors, or to send them to bodies or officials whose decisions or actions (inaction) are appealed against. In case of the need for additional information, references and materials for a complete, impartial and timely consideration of the appeal of persons who have sent a remote appeal, the official of the state body considering this appeal may request additional information from the physical or legal person who has applied, as well as from other state bodies within their powers.

If the information does not contain information constituting a state secret or other secret protected by law, does not harm the rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of individuals and legal entities, the interests of society and the state, state bodies, their officials are obliged to provide the requested information within ten days.

The state body considering the remote appeal may, if necessary, ensure consideration of the appeal on the spot. If it is impossible to consider an appeal in the absence of a person or other person who arrived at the reception, they may be summoned by an official of a state body.

If the summoned applicant does not appear, the official of the state body sends a reply that it is impossible to consider the appeal without his participation. Prevention inspectors consider the application or complaint within fifteen days from the date of receipt of the application or complaint to the state body, which is obliged to resolve the issue on the merits, and in the case of requiring additional study and verification, up to one month.

In cases where it is necessary for preventive inspectors to conduct an investigation, request additional materials or take other measures to consider applications and complaints, the deadlines for their consideration may be extended by the head of the relevant state body, as an exception, no more than one month, with the applicant notified.

In this regard, the conditions for the formation of new technologies, ensuring public order and security, peace and tranquility of citizens, the continuity of our traditions and values create an important condition. Therefore, the improvement of the powers of the internal affairs bodies in this regard will serve as a bold step towards reliably ensuring peace and tranquility in our country and our citizens

References:

1. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президенти 2017 йил 10 апрелдаги ПФ-5005-сонли “Ички ишлар органларининг фаолияти самарадорлигини тубдан ошириш, жамоат тартибини, фуқаролар ҳуқуқлари, эркинликлари ва қонуний манфаатларини ишончли ҳимоя қилишни таъминлашда уларнинг масъулиятини кучайтириш чора-тадбирлари тўғрисида”ги фармони <https://lex.uz/docs/3159827>
2. Smart mahalla <https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=uz.mvd.smartmahalla&hl=ru&gl=US&pli=1>
3. Ўзбекистон Республикасининг 2017 йил 11 сентябрдаги “Жисмоний ва юридик шахсларнинг мурожаатлари тўғрисида»ги Ўзбекистон Республикаси қонунига ўзгартиш ва қўшимчалар киритиш ҳақида”ги ЎРҚ-445-сон қонуни <https://lex.uz/docs/3336169>
4. Абдираимов, А., Абдуллаев, Ф., & Норқўзиев, С. У. (2022). Жамоат жойларида алкоголь маҳсулотини истеъмол қилиш ҳуқуқбузарлиги учун жавобгарликни

такомиллаштиришнинг айрим масалалари: мдх давлатлари қонунчилигининг тиббий, қиёсий-ҳуқуқий таҳлили. Eurasian Journal of Academic Research, 2(13), 212-217.

5.Халилов, Д. А. (2022). Зиёдуллаев Музаффар Зиёдуллаевич, Абдуллаев Файзулла Абдикодир ўғли.(2022). ИЧКИ ИШЛАР ИШЛАР ОРГАНЛАРИ Маъмурий чеклаш чораларини қўлловчи субъект сифатида. development of pedagogical technologies in modern sciences, 1 (2), 16–18. <https://doi.org/10.5281/z>. Development of pedagogical technologies in modern sciences, 1(2), 19-22.

6.Абдуллаев, Ф., & Муродов, Н. (2023). Фуқаролик жамияти институтларининг жамиятда тутган ўрни. Наука и инновация, 1(7), 98-101

